

NAA (0.5 mg/liter), 2,4-D (1.0 mg/liter), and benzyl aminopurine (0.5 mg/liter) without kinetin.

Temperature was maintained at 25 + 10 °C. Callus first appeared 22 d after inoculation.

Callus induction and development were more effective at 1,000 lx. Well-developed callus was 20% and poor callus, 66.6% when cultures were grown with light; they were 0% and 53.33% when cultures were grown in darkness,

indicating that light has some effect on callus induction. Further growth and development was measured weekly. After 8 wk in culture, the callus grew sufficiently for subculturing.

Subculturing was done in the same medium. Initially, growth was slower, with a callus doubling time of about 8 wk. But with frequent subculturing, callus doubling time was reduced to 5 wk.

Under the microscope, no *Anabaena* cells were found in mature callus cells (see figure). This indicates that *Anabaena*-free *Azolla pinnata* cultures can be produced through tissue culture of leaf explants. It could be possible to isolate *Anabaena*-free *Azolla* protoplast from these calli which could be utilized for future somatic cell fusion experiments with improved N₂-fixing *Anabaena* cells. □

Cultural practices to reduce winter damage to rice

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In the tank-fed areas of southern Karnataka India, cold temperature-sensitive rice varieties planted after the first week of Sep fail to produce any grain. The main cause is high susceptibility to low temperature at flowering. Local cold-tolerant varieties S705, S317, and Mangala fail because of heavy disease pressure. We tested postponing flowering time by cutting tillers to 10 cm at varying times after transplanting. Six varieties with varying maturities were sown 11 Sep 1985 and transplanted 10 Oct 1985.

Cutting up to 74 d after seeding (DAS) did not delay flowering because the primordia was unaffected (Table 1). Cutting 84 and 96 DAS markedly

Table 1. Effect of pruning on days to 50% flowering of winter rices. Bangalore, India, 1985.

Entry	Days to 50% flowering					
	No cutting	54 DAS	64 DAS	74 DAS	84 DAS	96 DAS
ES18	94	100	100	110	127	131
Mangala	104	110	111	113	126	131
IR19743-25-2-2	100	103	107	110	114	126
IR18476-55-2	100	104	107	110	114	127
IR15579-135-3	114	126	126	127	131	133
IR9202-25-1-3	110	117	121	124	127	131

Table 2. Effect of pruning of winter rices on tillering. Bangalore, India, 1985.

Entry	Tillers (no.)					
	No cutting	54 DAS	64 DAS	74 DAS	84 DAS	96 DAS
ES18	14	16	15	19	18	15
Mangala	16	20	39	25	14	20
IR19743-25-2-2	19	18	14	17	16	15
IR18476-55-2	14	10	8	13	11	8
IR15579-135-3	12	10	9	14	13	12
IR9202-25-1-3	15	14	11	15	12	11

delayed flowering because the stem tip was pruned. Flowering delay due to cutting date varied by genotype. 11315579-135-3 could be delayed a

maximum of 19 d, ES18 could be delayed 37 d.

Plant height and tiller production did not vary because of pruning (Table 2). □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on rice yield

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We studied the effect of slow-release N fertilizers on grain yield, total N uptake, and fertilizer efficiency using Ratna variety during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons.

Soil was Gangetic alluvial clay-loam with pH 6.7, 0.35% organic C, and

Effect of slow-release urea materials on yield and fertilizer efficiency. Calcutta, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Total N uptake (kg/ha)	Fertilizer efficiency (%)
Control	2.0	2.9	34.28	—
Urea	2.9	3.9	58.31	24.03
Urea supergranule	3.0	3.9	60.69	26.41
Neem cake urea mixture	3.3	4.3	70.41	36.13
Lac-coated urea	3.3	4.3	77.48	43.20
Sulfur-coated urea	3.9	4.9	94.89	60.61
Bitumen-coated urea formaldehyde	3.9	4.8	93.64	59.36
Sawdust urea formaldehyde	3.7	4.6	85.76	51.48
Urea formaldehyde	3.6	4.5	84.60	49.37
Mean	3.3	4.2	70.81	43.45
SE (±)	0.66	0.69	6.82	5.13
CD (0.05)	0.37	0.37	—	—

0.078% total N. Available P, K, and Zn were 11.8 kg/ha, 368.5 kg/ha, and 1.68 kg/ha (DTPA extractable Zn). Soil CEC was 21.80 meq/100 g.

The trial was in a randomized block design with nine treatments and three replications.

All plots except control and urea

supergranule (USG) treatments received one basal application of 100 kg N/ha during puddling. USG was applied immediately before transplanting by pressing the granules below the surface soil with the foot.

Sulfur-coated urea (SCU) gave the

highest grain yield, N uptake, and fertilizer efficiency (see table). In our laboratory, bitumen is used to coat ureaform. Results are comparable to those with SCU. Ureaform formulations also showed a significant increase in fertilizer efficiency. □

Damaged seedling roots and grain yield

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We studied the effect of seedling root damage on grain yield during kharif 1985 and 1986. The treatments follow: roots were handled carefully to avoid injury, roots trimmed from the base, seedlings uprooted from semidry soil with the help of a spade.

Thirty-day-old Jaya seedlings were transplanted the first week of July and fertilized with 120-26-50-6 kg N-P-K-Zn/ha. All of the P, K, and Zn were applied basally at transplanting. N was applied in 3 equal splits: basal, 21 d after transplanting (DT) and 42 DT.

Experimental field was clay loam with pH 8.1, low N, and medium P and K.

Root injury did not affect grain yield (see table). In transplanting rice, uprooting seedlings with the help of a spade may minimize labor costs. □

Effect of root injury on grain yield, Kaul, India.

Treatment	Panicles (no./hill)	Grains (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
All roots intact	10	120	5.6
Roots 100% cut	9.5	128	5.5
Seedlings uprooted with spade	10	125	5.7

Performance of long-duration CR1009 with aged seedlings

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In the Cauvery delta during Aug-Feb

(samba season), transplanting of widely cultivated 165-d duration CR 1009 is sometimes delayed because of delayed receipt of water in the canal. We tested the performance of late-planted CR1009 during 1985-86 samba. Seedlings were transplanted 30, 40, 50, and 60 d after

seeding.

Plant height, panicles/hill, panicle weight, grain weight/panicle, 100-grain weight, and grain yield were not affected by planting up to 50 d after sowing (see table). Later planting reduced yield parameters and yield. □

Performance of late-planted CR1009 in 1985-86 samba, Aduthurai, India.^a

Seedling age (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Panicle weight (g)	Grain weight/panicle (g)	100-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)
30	92 a	8.5 a	4.11 a	3.82 a	2.38 a	5.40 a
40	89 a	8.9 a	4.27 a	3.92 a	2.30 a	5.49 a
50	88 a	9.3 a	4.09 a	3.72 a	2.25 a	5.65 a
60	87 a	7.5 b	3.54 b	3.24 b	2.18 a	4.43 b

^aIn a column, numbers followed by a common letter are statistically identical at the 95% level of confidence.

Preservation of *Azolla pinnata* germplasm

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Senescence and death of azolla during the summer is common in tropical areas. We have developed a technique to preserve germplasm of *Azolla pinnata*.

Surface-sterilized fronds were inoculated on sterilized N-free medium solidified with 0.9% agar. Cultures were incubated at 25 ± 1°C and illuminated

with cool white fluorescent light for a 16/8 light/dark cycle.

Growth of azolla was extremely slow compared to growth in a liquid medium (see table). The fronds remained green for more than 3 mo and, when transferred to a N-free liquid medium, continued to grow and develop faster. Viability of the fronds transferred to liquid medium was 100%. The azolla cultures also were easy to transport. □

Growth of *Azolla pinnata* in solid and liquid medium. Baroda, India.

Period (wk)	Fresh weight (mg)	
	Solid medium	Liquid medium
0	300 ± 20.0	300 ± 20.0
1	398 ± 20.6	698 ± 29.8
2	518 ± 22.1	1258 ± 34.0
3	780 ± 39.1	2638 ± 73.2

Ammonia volatilization loss in rice soils of Cauvery Delta

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We quantified NH₃ loss using different sources of N with basal and split application of 90 kg N/ha in Jun-Sep 1984. Experimental field soil was a clay